

Environmental Accounting Disclosure Practices by Companies: A Systematic Review of Literature

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Abstract

The numerous attentions being given to the issue of environmental concern has generated opportunities for important researches and standard reforms in environmental accounting disclosure practices by the companies.

Purpose – *The purpose of this paper was to systematically review how environmental accounting disclosure practices of companies impacted the sustainability objectives of the firm with a view to identifying gaps and advance recommendations for policy-makers and future studies.*

Design/methodology/approach *The Systematic Quantitative Assessment Technique (SQAT), was adopted to search for data used in the critical analysis of 78 peer-reviewed articles obtained from 7 high impact scholarly databanks. Majority of the articles reviewed were empirical studies*

Findings – *There were external and internal pressures exerted on the company to adopt sustainability practices. However, the coercive pressures did not necessarily bring about a real change in the organization. The forces of change were mainly the foreign partners, audit pressure and the allegations by stakeholders, with serious attention given to these as a result of the reputational significance which is strength to the company. The discussion therefore provides researchers with a critical view of the subject exposing researchable gaps that will assist policymakers globally on how to put in place necessary legal framework and disclosure requirements to tackle environmental challenges.*

Practical implications – *Clear regulatory frameworks, more direct engagement with companies and meeting the expectations of the local communities were considered as crucial factors to ensure there is a pathway for sustainability in the activities of concerned firms.*

Originality/value – *The paper develops a systematic review framework from the relevant studies in firms' environmental accountability disclosure.*

Keyword: *Environmental accounting, disclosure, environmental sustainability, Climate change, SQAT,*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Environmental concerns are becoming a front burner and a frequent discussion point drawn upon by governments, corporate management, scientists and other stakeholders alike, and for obvious reasons, irrespective of the economic or social status, issues like climate change has the potential to effect of us (Bello, 2018; Cho, Laine, Roberts, & Rodrigue, 2018; Almontaser, & Gerged, 2019). Beyond the increasing call for public determination for environmental action, it has been challenging for the world to understand the potential extent of economic disruption that environmental risks might pose (Cheng, Wang, Keung, & Bai, 2017; de Faria, Andrade, & da Silva Gomes, 2018). The biggest investors in the world have being under intense pressure over their role in climate change, as the focus on tackling global warming has been on oil, gas and mining companies even to other companies that finance fossil fuel producers (Chandok, & Singh, 2017; Chelli, Durocher, & Fortin, 2018; Khalid, Atkins, & Barone, 2019; World Economic Forum, 2020). These corporations have been promising since the past decades to come clean on their exposure to environmental risk and hazards and with pressure coming from stakeholders forcing them to do it. (Arthur, Wu, Yago, & Zhang, 2017; Alawiye-Adams, & Akomolafe, 2017; Bello, 2018) This has often put the burden on shareholder and auditors to intensify and challenge the manner adopted by managers to assess or complicate the impact of environmental accounting on financial reports (Dragomir, 2010; de Faria, et al., 2018; Gaudencio, de Oliveira, Curi, Santana, Silva, & Meira, 2018).). Currently, many investors are anxious about how firms are defaulting in recognizing the potential loss to asset values posed by environmental risk (Ismail, Rahman, & Hezabr, 2018). These industries may also be lacking in acknowledging the fact that the prices of fossil fuel will virtually decline because of the switch to embrace a low-carbon economy (Ascuí, 2014; Garner, & Lacina, 2019). This

may result in energy firms to abandon difficult to mine oil and gas in the earth as “stranded assets”(Jaggi, Allini, Macchioni, & Zampella, 2018). Coupled with this also is the other concern that the oil and gas firms are not making adequate provisions for contingent liabilities in the likes of fines and litigation that push Pacific Gas and Electric Corporation into compulsory bankruptcy after the wildfires experienced in California. Because of these, there are indications that managers and auditors are beginning to become conscious owing to this challenge (Talbot, & Boiral, 2018; Garner, & Lacina, 2019).

Environmental accounting is an effort to extend the scope of the accounting frameworks adopted in assessing the economic performance by accounting for the stock of those elements that were not recorded in published or private accounting books (Xu, Zeng, & Tam, 2012; Fatima, Abdullah, & Sulaiman, 2015; Gerged, Al-Haddad, & Al-Hajri, 2018). These gaps occur as a fact that the result of different costs of using nature was not appropriately captured, this is because there are being considered in many instances as externalities that may be shifted to others or deferred. While the positive externalities ie, the natural resources are been depleted and not being accounted for in the national accounts, the companies however, do record it as depreciation element (Benlemlih, Shaukat, Qiu, & Trojanowski, 2018). Degradation result from the depletion of renewable resources, these compound negative externalities as a result of the pollution and disruption of cyclic ecosystem systems (Rustam, Wang, & Zameer, 2019). Therefore, the elements of production and income for the firms on one hand, the consumption, saving, investment, and debts for the public sector on the other hand, which forms the basis of many economic decisions are defective or at least incomplete. Hence, at times these may be misleading when the immediate benefits are in actual sense losses on the long-run once the firm consumes the reproductive functions of the capital (Michaels, & Grüning, 2017). Although national accounting has been a vital driving force in this change, environmental accounting however, involves all the accounting frameworks, ranging from the national accounts, the financial accounting standards, and other accounts put in place to evaluate the costs-benefits of plans and projects (Sethi, Martell, & Demir, 2017).

Nevertheless, most firms currently only showcase their sustainability reporting as a component of the management storyline at the forefront of their annual reports (Garg, 2017; Talbot, & Boiral, 2018). This only shows the rate at which companies greenwash their sustainability credentials (Du, 2015; Nurunnabi, 2016; Depoers, Jeanjean, & Jérôme, 2016). While majority of this is of no use as a result of so many initiatives and standards on this that have confused users of accounts and companies themselves (Giannarakis, Konteos, Sariannidis, & Chaitidis, 2017), these firms portrayed themselves as a green model while cheating on sustainability tests (Comyns, & Figge, 2015; Momin, Northcott, & Hossain, 2017; Liu, & Yang, 2018). The big energy companies have been trumpeting their green efforts nevertheless they continued to invest furthermore in fossil fuels even more than in renewable sources (Bradshaw, 2010; Comyns, & Figge, 2015; Du, 2015; Obeidat, Al Bakri, & Elbanna, 2018). This is because they can afford to cheerfully assume the continuing lack of stringent legislation for the taxing of carbon dioxide emissions (Ascui, 2014; Depoers, et al., 2016; Giannarakis, et al., 2017).

Accounting Standard bodies have recently pointed out an important fact through the practice notes explaining that the environmental risks for reported assets and liabilities should be material, and therefore will matter for future corporate profits, dividends and wealth maximization (Prasad, Mishra, & Kalro, 2017). These concern specifically pointed out issues such as the stranded assets and depreciation which have been the concerned of institutional investors. The focus here, is that it is not adequate for directors to quantitatively make the impact of environmental-related risks, rather the Auditors must also be put on the enquiry for further information that should effect a firm’s investors or creditors where it is omitted, misstated or obscured. This issue matters because most investors are very concerned to minimize the impact of sustainability risk of change on their performance (Cormier, Ledoux, & Magnan, 2011; Merem, Twumasi, Wesley, Isokpehi, Shenge, Fageir, & Ochai, 2017; Bello, 2018).

Figure 1: Global Risks Interconnection

Source: World Economic Forum, (2020)

This increased pressure from stakeholders seeking large corporations linked with pollution to take action on environmental degradation which has resulted in the rapid growth of environmental, social and governance funds as an asset class (Sun, Salama, Hussainey, & Habbash, 2010; Healey, 2016; Sethi, et al., 2017; Rustam, et al., 2019). However, the Standard Boards have no powers to enforce this practice note, but their guidance maybe significant in most of globalized corporate sector which is meant to provide valuable information for investors in any engagement with the companies (Cormier, et al., 2011; Behram, 2015; Chandok, & Singh, 2017). There is therefore the need to academically enhance further the impetus for the disclosure requirement with studies to reveal how corporate bodies are responding to the financial provision in line with the Paris agreement's goals (Al-Shaer, Salama, & Toms, 2017; Ahmadi, & Bouri, 2017).

This study focuses on a critical review of relevant researches on environmental disclosure practices studies with the view to identifying gaps that may inform the possibility for future studies. In line with this objective, the next sections of this article provide a detailed discussion of SQAT methodology adopted in this study to search for peer-reviewed articles on the subject. This is followed by the results, discussions and way forward for future research from the findings. The last section focuses on the conclusion and recommendation where the limitations are stressed and prospects for further studies based on these limitations highlighted.

2. METHODOLOGY:

This study is anchored on a systematic review of an aspect of developmental energy economics, energy finance and policy focusing on the drive for environmental disclosure practices of companies and the impact on the firms. The methodology adopted for data collection is the Systematic Quantitative Assessment Technique in line with previous studies by Pickering and Byrne (2014). This study found SQAT to be logical, simple in application because it can easily be replicated, which an essential component of any good review is. Also, it was considered suitable because it aids the researcher to glaringly revealed research gaps to enable for further studies based on the articles under assessment.

Table 1 shows how the articles on environmental accounting disclosure practices by companies were sourced from 7 electronic databases: Cambridge, Elsevier, Emerald, HeinOnline, JSTOR, Springer, Taylor and Francis, utilizing “in the title of the article” search for a single combination for “environmental accounting disclosure” + “companies/firms/corporations”, on Google Scholar advanced search menu. Scholarly research papers published in English language journals on energy finance aspect of the subject were obtained. This process ensured that only 78 English scholarly papers which were found to be significant to the review subject were selected. The abstracts of the papers from the search were scrutinized to ensure that they were dealing with environmental accounting disclosure practices by companies. The degree of inclusion or exclusion of the searched papers in this process was therefore determined. In this critical review of literature, book chapters by authors and conference proceedings were excluded; peer-reviewed which are solely conceptual or empirical papers are used for the review and analysis.

Table 1: Descriptions for SQAT application

	Step	Application in the current study
1	Define topic	Environmental Accounting Disclosure Practices by Companies
2	Formulate research question	Critical research question: What are the drive and impact of environmental disclosure on firms' performance?
3	Identify keywords	“environmental accounting disclosure”, “companies/firms/corporations performance”,
4	Identify and search databases	7 databases utilized: Cambridge, Elsevier, Emerald, Hein Online, JSTOR, Springer, Taylor and Francis, “in the title of the article” search using two search combinations: “environmental accounting disclosure”, + “companies performance”,
5	Read and assess publications	Abstracts of papers found were read and assess to make sure that these were dealing with environmental accounting disclosure by companies subjects in environmental and sustainability finance policy. Literature from book chapters and conference proceedings were excluded; hence peer-reviewed which are either conceptual or empirical papers are used for the review and analysis.

Journal Titles

From each original research paper examining environmental accounting disclosure practices by companies, the following items of information collected were recorded in a tabular form for the purpose of analysis thus: (i) Journal(s), (ii) Number of Articles(s). This breakdown is as presented in Table 2, which reveals the numbers of articles in these journals publications that borders on the subject of environmental accounting disclosure. A number of high impact journals, 78 sampled in total, were the channels for the publication of these environmental accounting disclosure practices studies. The Emerald publication with (32) had the most articles for this review, it was followed by the Springers (20). While, JSTOR (15), HeinOnline (5) each, others are Taylor and Francis (3), Cambridge (2) and Elsevier (1) which had the least numbers of articles.

Table 2: Journals with articles on environmental accounting disclosure practices by the Companies

Journal Titles	Number of Articles
Cambridge	2
Elsevier	1
Emerald	32
Hein Online	5
JSTOR	15
Springers	20
Taylor and Francis	3

Source: Google Scholar search report, 2020

3. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section provides findings of the studies on the environmental accounting disclosure practices adopted by the companies in their global operations, it furthermore highlights the drive and impact of environmental accounting disclosure practices on firms' performance. The essence of this discussion is to identify possible gaps and make recommendations for possible solutions.

The analysis covers the following scopes for the articles under review: the methodologies adopted, data sources, the countries studied, drives and results obtained. Also, the following themes from the papers were presented: theoretical bases underpinning for the studies, practices and drives for the environmental reporting, the relationship between the environmental practices and organizational performance.

3.1 Time Distribution of Environmental Disclosure Articles

Based on the sampled articles, the base year for the studies concerned with environmental disclosure was 2010. A thought-provoking question to ask is; what level of importance have researchers given environmental disclosure research over the decade covered by publications in this study? To answer this question, the number of articles published were compared. During the period 2010 to 2014 studies in the area fluctuates, but interest in the subject picked up in 2015 (17 articles) with the increase in published work (Figure 2). This spike in interest may be as a result of a series of awareness and drive by stakeholders concerning environmental disclosure requirement by companies. However, publication dropped in 2016 (7 articles) with a subsequent rise in 2017 (14 articles) published. This downward trend continued with the subsequent decline in 2018 (12 articles) and 2019 (4 articles).

This shows that there is the need for environmental sustainability researchers to invest more time dealing with issues concerning environmental responsibility considering the fact that the increasing awareness will significantly improve the efficiency of the companies' operations in relations to the surrounding which in turn will improve the development world over. This is a worthy objective that is worth the time, effort and resources of researchers around the world.

3.2 Geographical Distribution of Environmental Disclosure Articles

Figure 3 shows the geographic distribution of the 78 environmental disclosure articles reviewed in this study. Generally, the analyzed countries are closely linked with the country of affiliation of the authors.

In relation to the most analyzed countries, the results highlight a large number of articles are focused on the United States (10), and Canada (4), in North America. Brazil has (2) being the most studied country from Southern America. From the European nations, the United Kingdom and France had (8) and (7) respectively, this is followed by Sweden, Norway, Italy and Netherland with (2) each, while Spain and Pacific Russia had (1) each. In Asia, China and India have (6) each which is the highest studies followed by Kuwait (3) while, Malaysia, Taiwan, Yemen, Bahrain, Bangladesh, Qatar, Hong Kong, Pakistan and Indonesia with (1) each. Australia also recorded (3). In Africa, Nigeria (7), Ghana and Sudan had (1) each of some of the researches on environmental disclosure as depicted in figure 3.

Within the sample, studies were also found that performed a comparative analysis of the countries, like Nigeria and South Africa (Oke-Samuel, 2017), between different regimes Chelli, et al., (2018).

It is important to highlight the analyses centered on developing countries, such as Nigeria, Malaysia, Bangladesh, Sudan, South Africa and Ghana. It has been acknowledged that the spurs for the practices of Environmental disclosure in Bangladesh, Nigeria, Sudan and Ghana can be credited to the pressure from the western customers, media, and institutions, through the channels of imposition of the operational policies and

the codes of conduct (cohesive isomorphism) (Che-Ahmad, Osazuwa, & Mgbame, 2015; Hassan, & Kouhy, 2015; Abdalla, & Siti-Nabiha, 2015; Usman, & Amran, 2015; Nurunnabi, 2016; Odera, Scott, & Gow, 2016; Arthur, et al., 2017; Alawiye-Adams, et al., 2017; Merem, et al., 2017; Oke-Samuel, 2017). The conclusion opined by Abdalla, & Siti-Nabiha, (2015) emphasized the role played NGOs in conjunction with other bodies as a result of the vulnerability of the countries, coupled with high levels of poverty, weak governance structure, over-reliance on external aids, and associated with the high level of corruption by political and corporate elites (Abdalla, & Siti-Nabiha, 2015; Usman, & Amran, 2015; Nurunnabi, 2016; Odera, et al, 2016; Michaels, & Grüning, 2017). In addition, the non-existence legal framework, the imperative of profit-making, poor performance justifies the absence of responsible environmental reports, these serve corporate interests and benefit the stakeholders (such as the management and shareholders) who are within the corridors of power (Dragomir, 2010; Fatima, et al., 2015; Lee, & Sweeney, 2015; Post, Rahman, & McQuillen, 2015; Arthur, et al., 2017; Alawiye-Adams, et al., 2017; Garg, 2017). The practices of providing environmental disclosure by firms are specific to the respective country in line with the prevalent context factors in the specific country.

3.3 Article Type

The 78 articles were grouped into two broad categories: conceptual and empirical. The conceptual articles were defined as those that focused and provided a theoretical debate on environmental disclosure, whereas the empirical articles were those associated with collection of data qualitatively and/or quantitatively in for the purpose of testing a particular to refute or support a hypothesis in the real world. Figure 4 showcase the breakdown of the 78 articles based on this classification.

The articles reviewed had only (13%) which are conceptual in nature, where the authors offered recommendations (Chen, 2010; Jones, 2010; Chu, et al., 2013; Ascui, 2014; Higgins, Milne, & Van Gramberg, 2015; Fazzini, & Dal Maso, 2016; Oke-Samuel, 2017) and theoretical models (Frynas, 2010; Chelli, et al., 2018) on how to improve transparency and accountability in environmental disclosure. The vast majority represented by (87%) of the articles were empirical studies (Bradshaw, 2010; Djajadikerta, & Trireksani, 2012; Chen, Cho, & Patten, 2014; Alon, & Vidovic, 2015; Arslan-Ayaydin, & Thewissen, 2015; Chiu, & Wang, 2015 Al-Shaer, et al., 2017; Chandok, & Singh, 2017; Prasad, et al., 2017; Arthur, et al., 2017; Obeidat, et al., 2018; Benlemlih, et al., 2018; Gaudencio, et al., 2018; Gerged, et al., 2018; Rustam, et al., 2019). This disparity signifies an clear gap in the environmental disclosure study which future research should address. While it is commendable that sustainability researchers are thinking about practical steps to minimize lax in disclosure, evidence based research will determine the extent of effectiveness these strategies are in achieving these laudable objectives.

Theoretical Frameworks

Figure 5: Theories Used

Based on the extant literature, this study seeks insight into the drivers for disclosure by the companies through the underpinning theories. A number of studies adopted either one or multiple theories as an explanatory theory of environmental disclosure. Various authors adopted legitimacy theory, stakeholders' theory, new institutional theory, political economy theory, signaling theory and host of other theories to underpin their studies. These different theoretical perspectives provide different information, which is complementary to the understanding of the corporate practices invoke in their disclosure practices. These theoretical frameworks adopted to support their studies in the reviewed papers are illustrated in figure 5. The legitimacy theory was predominantly applied theory in (13) articles, stakeholders' theory (12), new institutional theory (6), political economy theory (4), signaling theory (2) and others theories (1) each. Some of the other theories include the critical mass theory, agenda-setting theory, normativity theory, voluntary theory, amongst others.

Legitimacy and stakeholders' theories

Quite a number of researchers adopted the legitimacy theory to support the practices of environmental disclosure. According to Behram, (2015), the legitimacy theory in voluntary disclosure is an attempt to demonstrate the company's commitment to being environmentally responsible and to developing its activities in conformity with the society's values related to information disclosure. Therefore, companies attempt to legitimize themselves not only before society but also before the companies with which they do business the legitimacy theory suggests that environmental disclosure is the response by companies to both political and social pressures seeking to legitimize their activities in the longterm, to achieve stability in a voluntary 'social contract'(Fazzini, & Maso, 2014; Almontaser, & Gerged, 2019). Ferreira, Vila, Mariussen, Kuo, & Chen, (2013) have agreed that in response to these pressures, companies change the form (i.e., specific or general) and by an extension (either increase or decrease) the environmental disclosure report provided, so as to preserve their image and legitimacy. The environmental disclosure may create a different image of the organization by protecting it from external pressures.

Albertini, (2014) after the introduction of the 'New Economic Regulations' of the French law, which mandated for the disclosure of environmental facts by quoted firms, revealed that there a positive change in level of

environmental information disclosure as a result of the law. These are consistent with the corporate vision of the legitimacy theory because firms have begun to comply with the law to secure organizational legitimacy. It was also reported that companies in an attempt avoid sanctions as a result of the non-conformity with the existing legislations in the corporate environment, so that its image may be unaffected. De Faria, et al., (2018) using the theory of legitimacy also concluded that companies legitimize a newly discovered process of production by the 'manipulation' of the perceptions and the ideological alignment with the State.

While the stakeholders' theory on the other hand focuses on the interface and communication between the business and stakeholders. The stakeholders' theory stressed that companies with the best performances, disclose more on their sustainability performance (Fernandez-Feijoo, Romero, & Ruiz, 2014; Thijssens, Bollen, & Hassink, 2015; Chiu, & Wang, 2015). Also, companies in response to the external pressures of stakeholders, undertake some dissemination of information in an superficial attempt to project their corporate legitimacy (Haque, & Islam, 2015; Lee, & Sweeney, 2015; Thijssens, et al., 2015).

Institutional theory

The notion of legitimacy and the search for legitimacy are the pivot of the institutional theory. This theory focusing on identifying and analyzing those institutional pressures that may perhaps explain the behaviours and practices of organisations. Escobar, & Vredenburg, (2011) stated that businesses can only survive through the mean of an isomorphic transformation, which occurs through three fundamental mechanisms: coercive isomorphism, normative isomorphism, and mimetic isomorphism. Alon, & Vidovic, (2015) stated that businesses are expected to recognize how the environmental report is used as a response to the institutional pressures coming from the social context. They therefore concluded that the report standards have been changed due to transformation in the social and institutional variables as a response to institutional pressures in order to maintain their legitimacy in society. Likewise, as an answer to such institutional pressures, organizations are constantly adopting a voluntary environmental strategy for the purpose of effectively managing the environmental impacts of their processes, products or services (Xu, Zeng, & Tam, 2012; Ferreira, et al., 2013; Odera, et al., 2016).

Also, Haque, & Islam, 2015 agreed that environmental regulation can act as a booster for the changes in the firms' practices of environmental reporting (coercive isomorphism), through a significant increase in dissemination of the emissions in reports and accounts. Even though the quality of these dissemination is questionable, the firms considered that this introduction of the regulation can improve the disclosure. Analyzing the situation prior to and after the introduction of this particular legislation, Che-Ahmad, et al., (2015) concluded that institutional pressure coupled with the new legislation (coercive isomorphism) caused a significant rise in the level of environmental reporting, which also induced an increase in dissemination of the mandatory character, which maybe detrimental to voluntary dissemination.

Signaling theories

The signaling theories on the other hand propose that companies adopts information to signal their values in addressing social and environmental issues by ensuring and creating the awreness before the stakeholders that the issues are being handled by the companies (Dawkins, & Fraas, 2011; Garner, & Lacina, 2019). In this perspective, Du, (2015) stated that there are two procedures for signaling or 'ecological washing' for the purpose of information disclosure through the autonomous reports of social responsibility. Compelled by this signaling motive, companies disseminate the information as a mark of its high commitment. On the other hand, in relation to 'ecological washing', companies adopt the reports to showcase themselves as 'good' corporate citizens. Hence, the theory of signaling might elucidate the motivation for providing of the autonomous reports after some negative experiences with the media (Chelli, et al., 2018).

Methodology and Data Sources Used

In this section, the objective was to pinpoint the primary research method utilized in each of the 78 environmental disclosure articles reviewed. Figure 6 shows a summary of the findings. Most of the papers used in this study aim to analyze the environmental information disclosed by firms in their annual reports and other

environmental or sustainability reports, the most prominent methodology was: statistical models, such as in Bradshaw, (2010); Djajadikerta, & Trireksani, (2012); Chen, Cho, & Patten, (2014); Alon, & Vidovic, (2015); Arslan-Ayaydin, & Thewissen, (2015); Chiu, & Wang, (2015); Al-Shaer, et al., (2017); Chandok, & Singh, (2017); Prasad, et al., (2017); Arthur, et al., (2017); Obeidat, et al., (2018); Benlemlih, et al., (2018); Gaudencio, et al., (2018); Gerged, et al., (2018); Rustam, et al., (2019). Nevertheless, this method revealed some shortcoming because of the subjectivity in the explanation of the data collected and in the choice for the inclusion in either of the defined categories.

A large number of the studies reviewed (33%) adopted statistical models, as their primary research method. Typically, this involved studies dealing with environmental disclosure practices (Rahman, & Post, 2012; Momin, et al., 2017). These studies would analyze each component of the disclosure practices and identify the strengths and weaknesses in relationship with its ability to improve the transparency and the accountability of the companies (Frynas, 2010; Moniz, Jacoby, Meggs, Armstrong, Cohn, Connors, & Kaufman, 2011).

Survey method (da Rosa, Ensslin, Ensslin, & Lunkes, 2012; Ahmadi, & Bouri, 2017) and theoretical analysis which involved the use of simulations (Escobar, & Vredenburg, 2011; Higgins, et al., 2015; Healey, 2016) were the second and third most common research method, representing 24% and 12% respectively. This was closely followed by content analysis (Rankin, Windsor, & Wahyuni, 2011; Moniz, et al., 2011) representing 9% of articles reviewed.

The interview of stakeholders (Albertini, 2014; Thijssens, et al., 2015) and the use of environmental disclosure case study (Cheng, et al., 2017) were methods equally utilized represent by 8% and 6% respectively of the articles reviewed. Two articles (Dawkins, & Fraas, 2011; Chelli, et al., 2018) both adopted content analysis plus interview in their studies, thus completing the seven distinct research methods identified in this review of environmental disclosure studies.

Two opportunities for prospective environmental disclosure studies have been identified in relation to the research methods. From figure 6, it was revealed that majority of the past studies have adopted critical analysis. The opportunity for these future studies exist because most of the studies reviewed had adopted one or the other research methods. Therefore, future research may combine two or more research methods for the purpose of attaining greater insight into the different perspectives of the environmental disclosure as it pertains to improving transparency and accountability, and minimizing sustainability disruption.

Figure 7: Data Sources Used

However, some companies have adopted other sources of information disclosure, such as the CEO statement of declarations, sustainability or environmental reports, official brochures, news media, press releases, and websites (Ismail, et al., 2018). The longitudinal approach calls for an analysis of possible relationships between or among the context and/or behaviour in terms of disclosure of environmental information spanning a long period of time. Several studies resorted to this approach, as obtained in Albertini, (2014); and Liu, and Yang, (2018).

3.4 Practices and Drivers for Environmental Reports

This section focuses on practices and drivers for environmental disclosure by the companies. A wide range of studies examined the subject of environmental disclosure and reporting practices, these studies had taken into account different aims, by evaluating the extent and nature of practices of environmental disclosure prior to and after the introduction of the legal. The motivations for environmental disclosure are intrinsically related to managing the firm's reputation, the pressure of stakeholders, environmental accidents, legislative involvement or obvious for the fact that some of the organization has in place an environmental management system. Some even studies suggest that some companies engaged in environmental disclosure practices primarily to secure their own position or private interests.

This environmental disclosure information comes in many forms while some are qualitative statements, others are quantitative facts, and some could be in financial statements, graphics or photos, CEO declarations, amongst others. These maybe included in the annual report, or in a stand-alone report, or possibly in sustainability reports according to GRI, or in a press release, company websites, etc.

There has been revealed that most environmental dissemination tends to be strategic with the intent to legitimize the activity rather than promoting greater accountability. Also, an environmental accident may be the tendency to increase information dissemination mostly through press releases, advancing reasons on why and how the accident occurred and/or possibly the corrective measures. Hence to manage their reputational risk some organizations extensively use disclosure information on their websites (Rankin, et al., 2011; Djajadikerta, & Trireksani, 2012; Ismail, et al., 2018).

Comyns, & Figge,(2015) concluded that companies that has recorded a high environmental impact showcase them more in graphics for environmental information in contrast to the ones with less environmental impact. The Japanese companies has adopted this as the main drive for environmental dissemination, explained by their peculiar cultural differences (Thijssens, et al., 2018), following the ratification of the Kyoto Protocol, which set some tolerable limits for the emission of gases associated with greenhouse effects (da Rosa, et al., 2012; Chu, Chatterjee, & Brown, 2013; Depoers, et al., 2016; Liu, & Yang, 2018). However, in Nigeria's case, the Kyoto Protocol participation is not enough to result in net decreases in carbon dioxide emissions (Ascui, 2014; Hassan, & Kouhy, 2015; Momin, M. A., Northcott, D., & Hossain, 2017; Jaggi, et al., 2018).

Khalid, et al., (2019) concluded that firms operating in countries with working regulations which are actively concerned with environmental dissemination (France and the United Kingdom) report more on environmental information in comparison to other firms in jurisdictions with ineffective regulations on the environment. These results revealed that the IAS/IFRS are not consistently applied in all countries due to 'traditions' and differences in the legal requirements of each jurisdiction.

Another drive for environmental disclosure is the need for certain certification (Wang, 2016; Ismail, et al., 2018). Fernandez-Feijoo et al., (2014) have noted that the firm's internal regulations together with the supply chain stakeholders influence the decisions of managers to acquire environmental assurance. Consequently, the report for the purpose of environmental certification offers double benefits as it adds value to the management and stakeholders.

3.5 Relationship between Environmental Disclosure and Organizational Performance

In this category, the analysis focus on the relationship between the environmental disclosure and performance of companies.

Some studies conclude that there is no significant association between the profitability and disclosure in the short term, however, in the long run, the increase in disclosure is correlated with the evaluation of the market (Dragomir, 2010; Che-Ahmad, et al., 2015; Arslan-Ayaydin, & Thewissen, 2015). Other studies identified a positive association between the sustainability report and sustainability performance of companies (Depoers, et al., 2016; Liu, & Yang, 2018). The result is consistent with the study of Sun, et al., (2010); Alon, A., & Vidovic, (2015); Arthur, et al., (2017). Therefore environmental disclosure practices influence investment allocation decisions. However other studies identified a negative relationship between the environmental report and environmental performance of companies.

An organization with an environmental management system will influence environmental performance and reporting because the managers and other stakeholders are involved in these matters. Even though the positive association that exist between environmental performance and economic performance is largely to an extent generally accepted in the literature, the results analyzed however are not conclusive.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper reviewed 78 peer-reviewed journal articles dealing with motivation and impact of environmental disclosure practices by companies. These articles were examined along some key categories, including the time distribution of the articles, the geographical distribution of the article, journal titles, article type, and research methods. The results of the review were discussed and the agenda for future research were equally provided. Although quite a number of studies on environmental disclosure practices have been conducted, there are still significant opportunities for more empirical focused research in this area, mainly due to the crucial importance that disclosure practices plays in sustainability. This is even more appropriate for nations that are considered to be highly susceptible to environmental hazards.

Some limitations exist in this systematic review, which provides an additional gap which future sustainability research can explore. Whilst the databases were from high impact, peer-reviewed articles, these however definitely may not comprise all the peer-reviewed environmental disclosure articles. Therefore, subsequent systematic reviews may broaden the scope of databases better insight into this crucial research area. An additional limitation exists in the fact that only journal articles were used in the review whereas book chapters and conference proceedings were excluded. This was in line with the methodology chosen to ensure that only high quality articles were reviewed. We should be mindful of the fact that, there is great deal of potentially useful insight in book chapters and conference proceedings, which future research may deem necessary to be include. Also the fact that only title word search was utilized rather than a keyword search was a limitation. This is because, title word search provides a more precise search of articles that are dealing with environmental disclosure practices. However, a keyword search using terms such as sustainability reporting; integrated report; Global Reporting Initiative, and others would have generated a greater number of articles for the review. More so, quite a number of the papers might not have directly addressed environmental disclosure, but could have provided additional insight such as those concerning social and environmental sustainability.

However, despite these limitations, this study is important as it provides a clear picture on the current state of environmental disclosure practices research and gives clear direction on the areas that future research needs to address in order to create a more sustainability process to reduce environmental hazards to its barest minimum. In line with this perspective there should be a deliberate commitment to the society and environment from all and sundry, hence positively contributing to a better accountability and improved state of the environment.

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